

Supplement for: *Do little interactions get lost in dark random forests?*

Part 2: Single variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

Figure S1: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S2: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S3: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S4: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S5: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S6: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S7: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S8: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S9: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S10: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S11: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S12: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S13: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S14: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S15: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S16: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S17: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S18: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S19: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S20: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S21: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S22: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S23: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S24: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

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Part 3: Pairwise variable importance measures

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Figure S25: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S26: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S27: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S28: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S29: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S30: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S31: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S32: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S33: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S34: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S35: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S36: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S37: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S38: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S39: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S40: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S41: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S42: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S43: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S44: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S45: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S46: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S47: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S48: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

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Part 4: Ranks of marginal-only SNPs, single variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

Figure S49: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S50: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S51: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S52: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S53: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S54: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S55: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S56: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S57: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S58: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S59: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S60: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S61: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S62: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S63: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S64: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S65: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S66: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S67: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S68: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S69: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S70: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S71: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S72: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

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Part 5: Ranks of marginal-only SNPs, pairwise variable importance measures

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Figure S73: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S74: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S75: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S76: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S77: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S78: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S79: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S80: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S81: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S82: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S83: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$

Figure S84: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$

Figure S85: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S86: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S87: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S88: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S89: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S90: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S91: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S92: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S93: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

Figure S94: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S95: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.4, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 10$

Figure S96: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.4, mtry = 10$

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Part 6: Additional scenarios, single variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

1 Fewer marginal-only SNPs

Figure S97: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$. 2 marginal-only SNPs.

2 More SNPs than samples

Figure S98: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$, 2500 SNPs.

3 Correlated SNPs

Figure S99: $\beta_I = 0, \beta_M = 0, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S100: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S101: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S102: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S103: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

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Part 7: Additional scenarios, pairwise variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

1 Fewer marginal-only SNPs

Figure S104: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$. 2 marginal-only SNPs.

2 More SNPs than samples

Figure S105: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$, 2500 SNPs.

3 Correlated SNPs

Figure S106: $\beta_I = 0, \beta_M = 0, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S107: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S108: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S109: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S110: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

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Part 8: Additional scenarios, ranks of marginal-only SNPs, single variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

1 Fewer marginal-only SNPs

Figure S111: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$. 2 marginal-only SNPs.

2 More SNPs than samples

Figure S112: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$, 2500 SNPs.

3 Correlated SNPs

Figure S113: $\beta_I = 0, \beta_M = 0, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S114: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S115: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S116: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S117: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

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Part 9: Additional scenarios, ranks of marginal-only SNPs, pairwise variable importance measures

Marvin N. Wright, Andreas Ziegler, Inke R. König

1 Fewer marginal-only SNPs

Figure S118: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$. 2 marginal-only SNPs.

2 More SNPs than samples

Figure S119: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, MAF_I = 0.2, MAF_M = 0.2, mtry = 50$, 2500 SNPs.

3 Correlated SNPs

Figure S120: $\beta_I = 0, \beta_M = 0, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S121: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S122: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.4, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S123: $\beta_I = 0.4, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.

Figure S124: $\beta_I = 0.8, \beta_M = 0.8, mtry = 50$. Linkage disequilibrium.